

ISic1347

I.Sicily inscription 1347

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140845

1. [ἔζησεν ὀ]
2. [Ἀν]τῶν [ιος]
3. ἔτη ο',
4. τελευτᾷ [— —]
5. ἔζησεν ὁ Σ[α]-
6. τορνῖλος ἔ [τη . .' τε(λευτᾷ)]
7. τῆ πρ (ὀ) δ' #⁵⁶ κα [λ(ανδῶν — —)]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492956

EDCS 39101721

PHI 140845

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0528 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9496

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